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Conceptualizing EU Return Policy since 2000: time for a paradigm shift?

Introduction

Today, immigration controls are deemed crucial for nation states to exercise power over their territory and determine who belongs to their nation and who does not. Migration control measures 'sustain the image of the world divided into national populations and territories, domiciled in terms of state membership' (Walters 2002, 282). They therefore are 'world-configuring' (Balibar 2002, 79), as they regulate population movements and sort out who belongs where. This report details this ongoing management of the world's population into territories by conceptualizing the role and nature of return policies – particularly in the European Union (EU) – in this process and by empirically detailing its evolution since the early 2000s.

Broadly speaking, return policies regulate the compulsory relocation of non-citizens to their country of nationality and thereby reaffirm the 'proper place' that these individuals belong to (Anderson et al. 2011). While at the beginning of the twentieth century, the enforced return – especially in the form of deportation – of unlawfully staying residents was commonly considered unacceptable, it became 'utterly banal' at the end of the same century (De Genova & Peutz 2010). Indeed, the enforcement of these policies had long not been among the top priorities of many European nations and was considered a secondary instrument of migration control only. De Haas et al. (2018) empirically show that this changed in the early 1990s, when what they call "exit" (return) and border control policies both started to become more restrictive. The authors argue that this reflects the shift from assistance-focused return programs set up to return displaced persons to their countries of citizenship to an emphasis on enforcing coercive expulsions and financing readmission programs, facilitated by the rise of new surveillance and border control technologies. Similarly, Gibney (2008) aptly notes that the use of enforced returns has expanded especially after 9/11, which spurred a shift towards surveilling and securitizing "alien Others". Like De Haas et al., he also assesses this "deportation turn" as remarkable, since deportation had long been considered a secondary instrument of migration control by democratic countries that was resorted to relatively rarely and with a degree of unease (but see Walters 2002). Gibney and others detail that this was the case due to the controversial and complicated nature of deportation. Deportations are controversial because they represent a "cruel power" (Gibney 2008): they separate individuals from families and uproot people from communities where they might have resided for many years. Research has indeed documented that grassroots resistance to expulsion has proliferated across the Global North, especially when particularly "deserving" non-citizens such as children and families, are concerned (Rosenberger & Winkler 2014, Wittock et al. 2023). More fundamentally, deportation poses questions to the liberal nature of European nation states where sovereign coercive power is 'self-limited' (Joppke 1998, see also Noll 1999). Liberal states, according to Mau (2010, 341), are best understood 'as states organized around liberal principles such as freedom of choice for individuals and collectives, individual liberties, a distinction between public and private, the rule of law and individual rights, and a market economy'. In the context of deportation, liberal values such as human

dignity, individual freedom and proportionality may indeed clash with the exercise of coercive sovereign power (Ellermann 2009). Their very nature thus ensures that states cannot simply impose exclusive and rigorous border controls or mass deportation campaigns and need to minimize the use of outright coercion as a strategy of first choice (Gibney 2013a). Such self-limitation is particularly apparent in states deciding to sign international human rights declarations, and in the development and application of these by (domestic) courts.

Next to this controversy, deportation is also a complicated state power on a more practical level. Complications to the enforcement of return policies comprise of, amongst others, non-citizens disappearing from state sight and thereby not being “available” for states who wish to execute a return order. Executing return policy is in many ways dependent on the cooperation of non-citizens themselves (see below), who thus might disappear when the prospect of enforced removal becomes more realistic. Marxist-inspired accounts by amongst others De Genova (2002) and Gibney (2008) emphasize that it is subsequently expensive and time consuming to track down immigrants who disappeared “off the radar” and that doing this might clash with market needs for cheap, informal sources of labour. Second, migrants might become “unremovable” since deportation is an inherent international act: it needs the cooperation of migrants’ countries of citizenship before relocation can take place. Research has documented that some countries are reluctant to do so, due to the possible tensions that can arise between the latter and their diaspora (Adam et al. 2020), a loss of remittances and difficulties with reintegrating citizens who have been abroad for extended periods of time (Ellermann 2008). Resistance towards cooperation will especially be high, according to Ellermann (2008), when migration control policies are formulated unilaterally and do not recognize the costs that deportation would place on readmitting states. El Qadim (2014) emphasizes that the EU’s dependency on these states, such as Morocco, has provided them with a bargaining chip and translated to their empowerment on the international stage. Finally, deportation policies are also prone to criticism, especially when it comes to exclusionary and coercive measures like detention and recorded human rights infringements in return (border) procedures (Bhui & Bosworth 2022, Klaus & Szulecka 2023).

Despite this deportation turn and the continued interest in effectuating deportation, the abovementioned factors lead to what Gibney (2008) coined as a “deportation gap”: a persistent discrepancy between the number of non-citizens without the legal right to stay on EU territory and the number of deportations taking place in a given year. This gap led national and EU policy officials to innovate in the policy realm to counter the aforementioned controversy and complications that enforcing return brings about. In the following sections of this report, we will trace what such innovations have looked like at the EU level since the early 2000s up until today, and how return ought to be enforced. We do so based on a collection of 59 European Commission (EC) documents and by analysing 1) the normative underpinnings of these policy documents in their understanding of the “problem of illegalized migration” and return, and 2) the evolution of measures proposed to solve this alleged problem. Before detailing what this looked like, it is necessary to first clarify and conceptualize what (EU) return policy exactly entails. Across academic and policy debates, there seems to be a wide range of ways in which “return policy” is understood: as comprising of different dimensions (i.e. Czaika et al. 2023 on the “external dimension”), across different geographical locations (i.e. Marino et al. 2023 on “externalized return”), as well as for varying aims (i.e. Bendixsen 2020 on “care and control”). What all of these have in common, however, is that they understand return policy primarily as a mere *enforcement mechanism*: a set of juridical measures that logically follow from immigration policy’s entry provisions and relocate ‘uprooted’ individuals back to their

“proper homelands” elsewhere on the globe (see also Kalir 2017). While this is obviously an important part of return policy, we will first argue that it is not the sole one. This report expands this understanding by also tying (EU) return policy to citizenship provisions and its power to reify their normative qualities. Following the work of Walters (2002) and Anderson, Gibney and Paoletti (2011), we pose that return policies regulate and substantiate who gets to stay and belong to EU territory and under what conditions. They therefore actively police populations internationally and shape (national) membership ideals, notably through rendering populations *deportable*. The report below thus not only empirically shows how the turn to *deportation enforcement* have gained shape over the past two decades, but also detail how ideas membership and belonging feed into efforts to close the deportation gap, through the production of migrant deportability.

In section two below, we will first conceptualize return policy as a juridical enforcement mechanism tied to entry, and a normative set of rules that produce migrant deportability. Next to the prevalent evidence in the wider literature surrounding race and crimmigration (Stumpf 2006), we will also highlight the recent turn to “liminal legality” (Menjívar 2006) that renders large populations deportable, and hence widens the scope of return policy. In section 3, we will subsequently introduce the methodology deployed to detail the evolution of return policy as an enforcement mechanism in the European Union from 2000s onwards, guided by Hall’s (1993) framework for studying policy change and Bacchi’s (1999) approach to studying policy problematizations. In section 4, we will describe the evolution of the EU’s return policy’s enforcement mechanisms, which can be characterized by a surprising stability in its underlying policy rationale but knows a great variety in the policy instruments proposed to address this rationale. What remains stable is the problematization of the “deportation gap” and the securitized manner in which return is discussed, despite changes in measures proposed and implemented that seek to reinstate control. This will therefore lead us to conclude, in section 5, that instead of aiming for further policy change at the instrument level, it might be time for a paradigm shift in EU thinking on return. Not as a control-problem that can be solved by sustained Europeanization and security-oriented policy instruments, but by realistically acknowledging its shortcomings and understanding the limits to return in relation to the needs of migrants and European societies alike.

Understanding return policy as inherent to entry and citizenship: a conceptual framework

The 1648 Peace of Westphalia is often cited as the moment when the modern state system – with national territory and sovereignty closely knit together – came into being (e.g. in Mau 2010 but see de Carvalho et al. 2011). This present-day state system features a strict division between domestic and international space, with great capacity for states to secure control of resources and people on their territory. State control over the ‘legitimate means of movement’ (Torpey 1998) – the ability to control who enters, resides, and leaves the territory – arose gradually and did so in parallel to the state’s monopolization of the legitimate means of violence (Weber 1921). Human mobility had been regulated for centuries in the ages before, albeit by particular social groups and private entities that were until then constituted as authoritative (Torpey 1998). In the early 20th century and accelerated

by processes of decolonization, the emphasis was put on preventing the entry of non-nationals instead of preventing exit of in particular colonized subjects (Sharma 2020). This was made possible by the creation of elaborate bureaucracies and systems of registration using passports and identity cards, through which states could increasingly “embrace” their citizens (Torpey 1998). Indeed, as modern nation states also claim a right to determine for themselves who their citizens are, individuals can hardly escape the linkages made between ‘identity’ (qua citizenship status) and the regulation of international movement via identification documents. As Sharma (2020, 92) aptly describes, this shift has had enduring consequences for international mobility today: ‘by requiring that “aliens” possess identification papers marking themselves as such, these documents solidified the idea that states were distinct, enclosed “societies” which “must be defended” from Migrants (Foucault 2003)’.

Modern-day nation states and the international state system have thus grown increasingly reliant upon making strict demarcations between mutually distinct bodies of citizens: ‘the state, nation and society trinity is the natural, social and political form of our modern world’ (Wimmer and Glick Schiller 2002, 301).¹ Such commonsensical linkage of people to place and nation to territory has far-reaching consequences for people on the move: by losing a bodily connection to their national homelands, migrants and refugees become ‘uprooted’ and are no longer seen as trustworthy, ‘honest citizens’ (Malkki 1992, 32). It turns the movement of people around the world into an “exceptional activity” which should be regulated by the states whose borders they threaten to cross (Hindess 2000). The mechanism that enables this differentiation, citizenship, plays a fundamental role in rendering a global population governable, by dividing it into smaller subpopulations that belong to individual territories and their states. Citizenship therefore functions as a “marker of identification” that advises “state and nonstate agencies of the particular state to which an individual belongs” (Hindess 2000, 1487). At the same time, citizenship also allocates a particular package of rights and responsibilities to individuals by virtue of their membership to a polity. In this international state system, the sovereign right of these nation states to self-determine led to the “nationalization of political communities”, meaning that nation states are in principle geared at guaranteeing rights for members and not for non-members (Benhabib 2004). The rise of such nation state sovereignty against the sovereignty of individuals ensured that rights became embedded in domestic legal systems that nation states uphold for persons within their (territorial) jurisdiction. Indeed, Hindess (ibid.) argues that this broader system of governance makes it possible for states to discriminate in favour of their own citizens and by extension requires the regulation of movement from one national territory to another.

Such regulation happens through immigration policies: “rules (i.e., laws, regulations, and measures) that national states define and implement with the (often only implicitly stated) objective of affecting the volume, origin, direction and internal composition of immigration flows” (Czaika & de Haas 2013, 489). These immigration policies, first and foremost, regulate who gets to *enter* a nation state that is not their own by virtue of their citizenship status and under what conditions entry can take place.

¹ In the EU context, there are two important remarks to make on the link between deportation and territory. First, various “non-entry clauses” are used in EU border management to deter the entry of illegalized migrants regardless of their physical presence. This happens in “transit zones” such as airports and seaports and can be extended further “inwards”, signifying that persons who are physically present are not considered to have “legally entered” EU territory. Second, the EU’s efforts to deport to date extend their territory, as exemplified through their externalized “pre-arrival return” activities in so-called “transit countries” (see section 4.2 for further explanation).

Present-day, much of the regulation of international travel is arranged through visa policies, which permit visa holders ‘to arrive at the border of the issuing state, and, subject to further checks, to pass for a specific period of time’ (Guild 2001, 31, quoted in Mau 2010). Some categories of people are permitted to enter nation states without having acquired such a visa first, for example when they are seeking entry based on humanitarian grounds, when fleeing persecution or indiscriminate violence. In the early 2000s, various sociologists (Bauman 2002, Shamir 2005, Urry 2007) predicted that a new system of stratification was emerging between those who can cross borders with ease and those for whom this is not the case. They link such “stratified mobility” to processes of globalization and widened inequalities. Bauman (2001) sees globalization as a distinct phase in modernity, characterized by speed, instantaneous episodes of social life that no longer seem linked together, and a sense of having lost control. Importantly for migration governance, Bauman understands transformations of the global free market as a key departure from previous episodes in modernity, with severe consequences for territorial sovereignty. As the flow of capital gains momentum, it becomes increasingly difficult for national governments to control this flow of capital between the free markets in the world economy, which led to a “crisis” for the role of local, territory-bound modern states. Bauman (1999) argues that this uncertainty and insecurity felt by citizens leads governments to demonstrate their determination in unloading these accumulated insecurities onto local targets, for example by waging war on those who disrupt their once familiar national backyard. On the international level, Shamir (2005) further developed this idea and argues that globalization and the emergence of a global human rights regime spurred new inequalities in mobility, not based on the power of nation states to fully block access but by virtue of a perceived, universal, dangerous “personhood” that he refers to as “a paradigm of suspicion”. This paradigm constructs individuals and countries as having “suspect identities” related to risks of immigration, terrorism and crime. Shamir (ibid.) situates the emergence of such a paradigm within processes of cultural and normative globalization that pose challenges to notions of bounded territoriality and citizenship rights. On a global scale, this thus leads to a stratification of mobility rights, where access to mobility is tied to the perceived threat that individuals and their countries alike are deemed to pose to the nation state. Return policy and the role it plays is intrinsically connected to entry, as the act of deportation “represents the compulsory allocation of subjects to their proper sovereign” and “serves to sustain the image of the world divided into ‘national’ populations and territories, domiciled in terms of state membership” (Walters 2002, 282). Indeed, asylum seekers whose application for international protection has been rejected, tourists who overstay their visa, or unauthorized labourers who were found in workplace raids do not or no longer meet the conditions tied to their entry to the nation state. Return policy then reaffirms the legal power that citizenship has in our present-day state system: it functions as a juridical mechanism to reallocate ‘uprooted’ individuals to their proper homelands (Walters 2002) and thereby enforce the rules set through entry policies. In this view, return policy serves primarily as an *enforcement mechanism*. In section 4 of this report, we will detail what the evolution of this enforcement has looked like at the EU level over the past two decades.

A separate set of rules and regulations determine under what conditions non-citizens are able to acquire *membership* of that particular nation state after having gotten entry to the territory. These rules and regulations also constitute return policy to the extent that they allow the state to end a migrant’s lawful stay, such by withdrawing a residence permit when a foreigner has committed certain crimes (see Leerkes et al. 2012 on ‘status reclassification’) or when the state believes that certain asylum residence permit holders no longer need to be protected against return because the conditions in their country of nationality have improved (i.e. in Brekke et al. 2021). While it exceeds beyond the scope of this report to clarify what such membership criteria exactly entail, it often

covers a temporal period of legal residence on the nation state's territory and proof of "good moral character" tied to economic or cultural markers of "desirability" (i.e., Goodman 2013). These normative criteria tied to membership are co-regulated by return policy, as it *expresses and shapes common identity within a political community*. This insight, developed by Anderson, Gibney and Paoletti (2011), highlights that return policy does not only shape the nation state as a community of law but also as a community of *value*. Whether, when and how people become susceptible to the exclusionary power of return policy – on what grounds they are rendered "deportable" (De Genova 2002) – is indeed also related to the normative character of citizenship. As Anderson et al. (2011, 548) argue, "the act of deportation establishes, in a particularly powerful and resonant way, that the individual is not 'fit' for citizenship or further residence in the society in question". Outright deporting an individual, or selectively reclassifying their immigration status from lawful to unlawful, shows that the state wishes to cut ties of legal and moral responsibility of said (non-)citizen, which in turn reaffirms the common identity of the nation. Wider literature on the construction of migrant deportability have emphasized the importance of securitization, criminalization and race. De Genova (2007) and de Noronha (2020) for example, highlighted the role of discourses of fear and insecurity, especially in the aftermath of 9/11, for creating a rationale that supports growing levels of detention and deportation for black and brown people. Bosworth (2008) highlights that there has been a growing reliance on criminal justice discourses in the construction of immigration and asylum policies. Overwhelming evidence suggests that appraisals of "bad moral character", sometimes but not always combined with immigration breaches or (minor) criminal conduct, indeed facilitate the deportability of (racialized) non-citizens across Europe (Bosworth 2008, Hasselberg 2018, de Noronha 2020), the US (Stumpf 2013, Menjívar & Gomez Cervantes 2018), Australia (Weber & Powell 2020). Less readily acknowledged in the literature on migrant deportability, however, is its inherent temporal dimension: migrants with various legal statuses (including temporary and indefinite ones!) remain susceptible to the state's deportation power – and therefore deportable. Various authors highlight a trend of citizenship becoming more "probationary" (Kostakopoulou 2013) and thereby an increasing "temporal uncertainty" (Griffiths 2021) for non-citizens. Schultz (2020) for example details that post-2015, several European countries reoriented the criteria embedded in their refugee policies from inclusion (who qualifies for refugee status) to exclusion (who can return, how fast, and to where?). This "return turn" in refugee protection, according to Schultz, ensured that refugees were only given a temporary residence status for an extended period of time which indeed increased their vulnerability to the state's deportation power. An extreme form of this is denationalization (Gibney 2013b): the revocation of citizenship as a punishment for certain types of behaviour, such as disloyalty or having committed a serious crime. Tripkovic (2023) argues that citizenship revocations indeed exclude individuals who are perceived as non-ideal citizens and thereby reiterate a view of citizenship at the intersection of communitarian and liberal ideals. Communitarian, as it excludes "suspect citizens" of foreign descent, and liberal as it primarily targets those whose actions, norms and values are deemed to repudiate liberal values. Brekke et al. (2021) detail how the increased turn to revocation of permits in Norway leads to severe consequences for the Afghan and Somali residents core to their work. Not only do they experience a prolonged sense of "liminal legality" – an uncertain limbo between permanence and temporality – but they also subsequently suffered from "disintegration": not knowing what their future would look like led them to orient themselves not simply to life in Norway, but also towards a possible exit and life elsewhere.

Summarizing, we have argued so far that return policy should be understood as tied to the international state system and its population management in two ways. First, it is an inherent part of highly-selective immigration entry regulations that reinforces and sustain the nation – territory –

state trinity. Here, return policy is seen as an enforcement mechanism to (re-)order national populations to the territories they belong in terms of state membership. But secondly, return policy is also a normative vehicle through which membership ideals get substantiated. Return policy implicitly sustains the common norms, ideals and identity of nation states by producing migrant deportability, declaring who cannot (or no longer) be part of the community of value (Anderson 2013). Based on a review of relevant literature, we detailed that return policy substantiates not solely ethnoracial hierarchies and ideals on “good moral character”, but also the “liminal legality” that non-citizens increasingly face in the Global North.

Following this conceptualization of return policy, the paragraphs below will describe the evolution of this policy field at the EU level. In doing so, it is guided by Hall’s (1993) foundational work on the evolution of British macroeconomic policy. Trying to understand the role of social learning for policy change, he describes three basic elements of policy that tend to shift over time. So-called first-order changes take place at the most concrete level and concern changes to operational settings or calibrations of policy instruments. A good example of this are budgetary changes commonly made in the light of new experience or knowledge, while the instruments deployed and the goals guiding policies remain the same. Second-order changes consist of changes made to the instruments deployed to achieve particular policy goals, while the overall (hierarchy of) policy goals remain the same. Finally, Hall details third-order changes as a change in the more-or-less abstract (hierarchy of) policy goals that underlies a particular course of government action. For British macroeconomic policy, Hall describes the radical shift from Keynesian to monetarist modes of macroeconomic regulation. In distinguishing these three levels, Hall makes an analogy to Kuhn’s (1953) work on paradigm shifts in the social sciences. The first and second-order changes above fit within “normal policymaking” (an analogy to Kuhn’s “normal science”), as these adjust processes but do not fundamentally change the overall nature or terms of a policy paradigm. Third-order changes, instead, reflect a very different process and involve radical changes to the overarching normative orientation of policy, which are associated with so-called “paradigm shifts”. This last process, therefore, is far more disjunctive and often classified as policy discontinuity. This analogy to paradigm shifts makes clear that changes in policy are, according to Hall (1993), dependent on ideas and thereby on discourse. He cites Anderson (1978), who argues that “the deliberation of public policy takes place within a realm of discourse... policies are made within some system of ideas and standards which is comprehensible and plausible to the actors involved”. Indeed, officials in the policy realm – those drafting and implementing policy – work within a framework of ideas that direct not simply the normative goals of policy and the kinds of instruments that should be used to attain these, but also the nature of the problems they are meant to address in the first instance (see also Schmidt and Radaelli 2004, Schmidt 2008, Bacchi 1999).

Methodology

Based on the abovementioned conceptualization and Hall’s (1993) model on policy change, the sections below will detail 1) the normative goals that underlie EU return policy since the early 2000s, 2) the enforcement instruments that are proposed and deployed in return policies, as well as 3) important changes in the calibrations of these enforcement instruments. In order to do so, we – the authors of this report and a research assistant – analysed a total of 59 policy documents from (predominantly) the European Commission (EC) that could provide us insight in the evolution of this policy field. We decided to focus on EC communications, as they have the sole legislative initiative in

the EU. While the Council and European Parliament can request legislation, the EC formally has the power to refuse to do so. Once legislation is passed by the Council and Parliament, it is also the commission's responsibility to ensure that it gets implemented, through providing guidance to member states and their executive agencies, such as Frontex. In view of the aforementioned "deportation gap", it is therefore essential to focus on how the EC proposes to "solve" the alleged problem of implementation. A full list of the policy documents reviewed can be found in the annex of this report.

For the selection of documents, we first drafted a timeline that included the "major milestones" on EU migration policy in general, and return policy in particular, over the past two decades. We started from the major annual frameworks in the area of Justice and Home Affairs that detailed migration policy proposals and narrowed down to specific return-related documents from there. These for example include the 2002 Green Paper on "a Community policy on 'illegal residents'", the 2015 "EU Action Plan on Return", the 2017 "Partnership Framework" and the 2021 communications on "Enhancing cooperation on return and readmission" as well as "The EU strategy on voluntary return and reintegration". Starting from these key texts, we followed an "intertextual reading" (Schwartz-Shea and Yanow 2012, 86) by following references made in these documents to other (foreseen) EC policy texts. Intertextual readings of this sort look for both ambiguity and contradiction across the broad range of meaning-making texts, without presuming or privileging one or the other. The newly found documents were added to the timeline when they sufficiently detailed a foreseen approach to EU return policy, either in its internal or external dimension. At the same time, we used the EUR-lex databased on EU law² to search for EC communications using key words such as "return", "voluntary return", "removal", "readmission", "illegal" and "irregular" for the 1999 – 2023 period. The EUR-lex website allows users to search for relationships between documents and classify them according to relevance on keywords. Combining the efforts of both strategies, we eventually ended with the abovementioned 59 documents.

In terms of analysis strategy, we follow interpretative and critical approaches to policy analysis and take particular inspiration from frame analysis. Following Goffman (1974), a frame is an interpretation scheme that structures reality. Critical approaches to frame analysis, especially those put forward by Bacchi (1999) and Verloo (2005), start from the assumption of multiple interpretations in policy and seeks to address such implicit or explicit interpretations. They do so by focusing on different representations that actors offer about the policy problem and the solutions at hand, and thereby expose the frames that inform actors' normative understanding of the policy problem and the consequent actions that are deemed appropriate to tackle the problem. Critical Frame Analysis (CFA) as developed by feminist policy scholars (Verloo 2005) puts particular emphasis on voice, roles, and context as crucial for shaping problem representations. It is informed by post-structuralist policy analysis (Bacchi 1999) that similarly focuses on the way policies *produce* problems as particular kinds of problems. Bacchi's 'what's the problem represented to be' approach (WPR) pioneered studying the way problems are represented and constituted in policies, directing attention to political rationalities and techniques of government. It takes an interest in disentangling the normative dimensions of policies, the 'deep-seated presuppositions' (Bacchi 1999, 48) and 'conceptual prejudices' (Verloo and Lombardo 2007, 37) that structure them, and thinks about the dimensions left unproblematic or unaddressed. In the analysis, we paid particular attention to both the explicit and declared intentions in policy narratives concerning the need for measures on return and readmission, and the implicit and tacit understandings that render these statements intelligible.

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/advanced-search-form.html?locale=en>

Following our interest in exposing the normative policy goals that underlie EU return policy and the enforcement instruments foreseen, such a critical approach to policy analysis provides useful tools to disclose the evolution of these two dimensions. Before detailing what this evolution looked like, we will discuss a few final caveats on the chosen methodological approach. The first obvious limitation lies in limiting ourselves to analysing EC communications only. While this seems a justified choice, given the EC's legislative mandate, there are at least two further important actors within the EU that we could have considered. The first one is the European Parliament, and especially their LIBE committee, whose critical reading of EC proposals on migration policy in general but return in particular, are important to trace the evolution of this policy field. The same goes for the Council, as both actors need to approve proposed legislation before it enters into force. Given that so far, there has been little effort to detail the evolution of EU return policy from a critical perspective (see Cassarino 2010 for an exception), we argue that focusing on EC communication provides for a good start that could later be extended by analysing other documents. Second, some documents that are likely of importance to shed light on the evolution of EU Return Policy are not publicly available, especially when they cover its implementation dynamics (see a.o. Carrera et al. 2018). A clear example are documents that detail the contents of so-called Joint Readmission Committees (JRCs): meetings where the EU, Frontex and third states discuss the implementation of concluded readmission agreements or arrangements (see also section 4.2 below). Finally, the literature on EU migration policy has highlighted that the EC has made a purposeful effort to “mainstream” migration policy matters into adjacent policy domains of development, visa, and trade, especially when it comes to cooperation on readmission (Roig & Huddleston 2007, Trauner & Kruse 2008, Carrera 2018). Accelerated after the Global Approach to Migration and Mobility in 2010, negotiations on return and readmission policy also take place in regional dialogues, such as the Rabat Process, the Budapest Process and the ACP-EU Migration Dialogue. This leads to relevant policy texts on especially the external dimension of return to be “scattered” across a wide range of policy domains and fora. While our sampling approach ensured a robust search for the most relevant documents based on keywords and intertextual referencing, we do want to be cautious about overstating the full width of our analysis. Our qualitative approach inevitably led to a necessary downsizing of the sample, which might have caused omissions in detailing the evolution of this policy field in all its facets. Despite this, we are confident that we have included the most relevant documents that detail whether and how the normative policy orientations and enforcement instruments have changed over the past two decades. Throughout the second part of this report's empirical section, finally, these changes are illustrated by graphs compiled on the basis of descriptive statistical analysis of Jean-Pierre Cassarino's Inventory of EU and Bilateral Agreements on Readmission.³ This database contains insightful, quantitative information on trends that the sections below also touch upon, in the areas of issue linkage, the importance of implementation and type of agreements. The sections below will outline what these and other developments look like.

Developments in EU return policy since 2000

This section details the evolution of EU return policy since the early 2000s, with a focus on detailing the possible changes in normative policy orientations and goals, as well as the development of

³ <https://www.jeanpierrecassarino.com/datasets/ra/>

different enforcement instruments that have been proposed to tackle “the problem of return” (Noll 1999). For purposes of readability, the section below will describe these evolutions along the five major annual frameworks in the area of Justice and Home Affairs in these two decades. These include the Tampere Program (1999-2004), which laid the groundwork for the development of a common EU policy on migration and asylum, followed by the Hague Program (2005-2009), which built the foundation for EU external border policy and cooperation with third countries. As shown in the section below, return policy programming accelerated from the Stockholm Programme (2010-2014) onwards, towards providing a comprehensive approach to migration management with the emphasis on comprehensive “partnerships” for return. The 2015 European Agenda on Migration called for a more coherent approach to EU return and readmission. This was continued in the final multi-annual framework to date, namely the recently adopted New Pact on Migration and Asylum proposed in 2020, which also saw the establishment of a new EU Return Coordinator. In short: our analysis shows that even though the underlying normative policy orientations remain fairly stable across the past two decades, there are a myriad of policy instruments proposed, forgotten and (on some occasions) reinvented. Below, I will explain these developments in more detail.

Normative policy goals: securitizing migrants, controlling member states and third countries

The analysis of the documents shows that there is a fairly stable discourse on **securitization** informing the imagined “problem” of illegalized migration and return from its inception in 1999 to present-day. The securitization of migration implies that security has become the central trope referred to when justifying strict migration control policies, as it ‘delegitimate[s] the presence of immigrants, asylum-seekers and refugees’ (Huysmans 2000, 753, also Shamir 2005). Huysmans’ argues that migration in the European context gets connected to threats they allegedly pose to public, social and cultural security – especially the former was referenced at length in the documents analysed for this report. During the first five years, when the European Commission started to shape a common EU return policy (Tampere Program 1999-2004), we see a clear setting of the tone for the “problem of return”. Policy documents clearly understand (the alleged lack of) return and presence of illegalized migration to and on EU territory as a security problem that needs to be solved. They thereby often put illegalized migration in the same “column” as other security and law-and-order issues, to emphasize the threat that it would bring to Europe. This is articulated most clearly in the policy document outlining the 2011 Global Approach to Migration and Mobility, as it stipulates that

“migration and mobility are embedded in the broader political, economic, social and security context. A broad understanding of security means that irregular migration also needs to be considered in connection with organised crime and lack of rule of law and justice, feeding on corruption and inadequate regulation”.⁴

Indeed, in this and other documents, illegalized migration is consequently presented as a phenomenon that needs to be “prevented” and “flighted” – language that occurs repeatedly across the first decade – most importantly due to its alleged linkages with organized crime networks that facilitate such movements⁵ as well as trafficking and economic exploitation.⁶ In these documents, the EU is clearly positioned as a community that is vulnerable to threats that illegalized migration, globalization, or even mobility at large poses to them. The 2010 document outlining the Stockholm Programme for example clearly juxtaposes people in need of protection, international students,

⁴ COM(2011) 743 final, p.15

⁵ COM(2001) 672 final

⁶ COM(2001) 672 final; COM(2003) 323 final; SEC(2004) 1349

tourists and other people “on the move” with the security of EU citizens, presenting tightened border management and an expansion of visa policy as a solution to achieve security in a globalized world (see also Shamir 2005). In order to regain a sense of security, these forms of mobility – and illegalized migration in particular – need to be “combated” through stringent return policy, especially because of its alleged linkages with organized crime, trafficking and smuggling.⁷ Until 2010/2011, this understanding of illegalized immigrants as threats to the (EU) citizenry through the challenges they pose to the rule of law, predominantly through alleged engagement in criminal and terrorist activities, further consolidated. The policy document detailing the contours of the Hague Program (2005) for example stipulates that “the citizens of Europe rightly expect [...] a joint approach to cross border problems such as illegal migration, trafficking and smuggling in human beings, terrorism and organized crime, as well as the prevention thereof”,⁸ again directly equating unauthorized movements with security issues.⁹ When discussing the need to draft a common return policy, the document stipulates explicitly that “the proposal should also take into account special concerns with regard to safeguarding public order and security”.¹⁰

Underlying this securitization of illegalized migration and return is a stringent, binary categorization introduced in the 2002 Green Paper between persons who reside legally on the territory and *want* to return over the course of time, and “illegal” migrants who reside unlawfully on EU territory and *need* to return.¹¹ Whereas the former group, so the document specified, should be assisted and helped in their decision to return¹², the latter is positioned primarily as an “object of intervention” in the documents. Intervening is important, so the EC argues, in the light of the (legal) **legitimacy** of EU migration and asylum policy. Indeed, a commonly referenced rationale concerns the integrity of EU policy measures (also extending the realm of migration governance), EU institutions and even the wellbeing of “migrants”. These are allegedly all at stake in case return policy should not be executed. A 2011 communication clearly stipulates this, by arguing that

“dealing firmly and effectively with irregular migration is a precondition for a credible migration and mobility policy. A low probability for of return for irregular migrants who are not in need of international protection is a pull factor and undermines public trust in national and European authorities”.¹³

Until the Stockholm Program and the Global Approach to Migration and Mobility, there was little referencing broader humanitarian concern for the welfare of returnees and illegalized migrants. Human rights and safeguards are routinely mentioned in the abovementioned documents, albeit in general and non-specific manners.¹⁴ Already in this first period, documents do underscore the need to “assist” third countries in return: “the possibility of developing a return policy that would avoid negative effects on the situation in these countries should be carefully considered” as “returning people on a large scale could have considerable impact on the development of a country [...]”.¹⁵ From the early 2010’s onward, however, do we see a clear **fusion of securitization with a humanitarian**

⁷ C (2010/C 115/01)

⁸ Council 2005/C 53/01, p.1

⁹ Also in COM(2005) 491 final; COM(2006) 402 final; SEC(2009) 766 final

¹⁰ Council 2005/C 53/01, p.6

¹¹ COM(2002) 175 final

¹² COM(2002) 703 final; COM(2002) 175 final, also in SEC(2011) 1353 final

¹³ COM(2011) 248 final, p. 9; also in COM(2006) 402 final; COM(2011) 743 final; COM(2014) 199 final

¹⁴ See a.o. COM(2002) 564 final; COM(2005) 390 final; C 2005/C 53/01; CME 2005; COM(2006) 402 final; C 2005/0167 (COD); SEC(2009) 766 final

¹⁵ COM(2002) 175 final, p. 11

discourse: a ‘politics of compassion’ (Fassin 2011) that directs our attention to the suffering of others, spurring the need for compassion and assistance. Pallister-Wilkins (2015) argues that humanitarianism is instrumentalized by governing actors to account for ever-restrictive policy interventions, which is also something the analysis reveals about the development of return over time (see also Bendixsen 2020, Crane & Lawson 2022). An important 2014 communication on EU Return Policy for example pays ample attention to the “correct” use of coercive measures like detention (i.e., ensuring that member states do not cross maximum limits), to ensuring that there are safeguards and legal remedies for returnees available in all member states, and to paying due attention to the treatment of minors and other “vulnerable persons” in return procedures.¹⁶ From 2015 onwards, with the EU Agenda for Migration until present-day, when the New Pact on Migration and Asylum entered into force, there is a clear fusion of these two normative orientations in the alleged “problem” that proposals for EU return policy should solve. Return, firstly, continues to be associated with smuggling¹⁷, border-related issues¹⁸ and even terrorism¹⁹. More legalistic rationales highlighting the unauthorized nature of secondary movements within the EU that illegalized migrants allegedly engage in, emphasizing that they lodge false, repeated claims for asylum in the EU and thereby overburden procedures.²⁰ According to these texts, not stepping up efforts to return is not only harmful for the workings of EU systems, but it is also **unfair and illegitimate**.²¹ It is unfair towards EU citizens, as it undermines trust in the EU asylum system among them²² and diminishes the benefits that they enjoy in Schengen, due to the need to reinstate internal border controls.²³ It is also deemed unfair towards “genuine refugees” who qualify for protection in the Union, portraying the right to reside on EU territory as a zero-sum game.²⁴

Second, documents from 2015 onwards also contextualize and describe the felt pressure on EU migration systems as resulting from a broader context of violence, poverty and destabilization that refugees are faced with and causes them to leave.²⁵ Return, then, is presented as a “deterrent to help reduce unsafe and irregular migration, prevents exploitation of migrants by breaking the business model of criminal smuggling networks and to promote safe legal pathways”: part of a humanitarian solution to security-issues that the EU faces.²⁶ Return policy, thus, should lead to reinstating the security of the Schengen area, while it at the same time helps preventing “loss of life” along migration routes. Indeed, the documents highlight that increased efforts to return “reduces unsafe migration”²⁷ and “ensures that lives are saved as people who know that they do not qualify for legal stay do not need to depart”.²⁸ Humanitarian rationales are especially prominent when the documents cover AVRR programs, especially in the first common Assisted Voluntary Return and

¹⁶ COM(2014) 199 final

¹⁷ COM(2015) 240 final

¹⁸ COM(2018) 634 final; COM(2015) 240 final

¹⁹ COM(2018) 798 final

²⁰ JOIN(2015) 40 final; COM(2017) 200 final; COM(2015) 453 final

²¹ See also COM(2021) 120 final

²² COM(2015) 453 final; COM(2016) 85 final

²³ COM(2016) 85 final; COM(2017) 200 final; COM(2023) 45 final, also in slightly different terms in COM(2011) 743 final

²⁴ COM(2016) 85, see Crawley & Skleparis (2018) for a critique on this purported binary

²⁵ JOIN(2015) 40 final; COM(2015) 240 final; COM(2016) 385 final; COM(2016) 85 final; JOIN(2017) 4 final, COM(2019) 481 final

²⁶ COM(2023) 45 final, p.2

²⁷ COM(2021) 56 final; COM(2021) 120 final; COM(2015) 453 final

²⁸ COM(2015) 453 final; COM(2016) 385 final

Reintegration (AVRR) strategy proposed by the EC in 2021. In contrast to previous documents that mostly emphasized the individual responsibility of illegalized migrants to return, this document speaks about giving “returnees real opportunities, and taking into account their needs, expectations and prospects once returned”.²⁹

Next to this fusion of securitization and humanitarianism in the normative orientation of EC policy documents on return, there is also a clear normative orientation that seeks to **(re)install control** on the part of the European Commission. This underlying orientation gained traction mostly from the 2010s onwards, when a common EU policy on return was installed and evaluated in 2014. From that moment onwards, EC policy documents clearly problematize migration, asylum and return as problematic phenomena where the EU and its Member States have “lost control”. This lack of control is attributed to a wide range of causes, amongst others to the “sudden nature” of migration-related events, like the much-cited “refugee crisis” in 2015.³⁰ It is also consistently allocated to the (non-)cooperation on return on the part of third countries, who ensure that readmission negotiations are “difficult”³¹ and “lengthy”,³² would not allow for forced removals or the use of charter flights, nor answer to requests for substitute travel documents – basically, do not “cooperate” with the EU on return nor abide by internationally recognized legal norms.³³ Policy documents again draw on legalistic frames to substantiate these claims, by arguing that third countries have a legal obligation to take their nationals back or are legally required to cooperate when readmission agreements or arrangements have been made.³⁴ Interestingly, this loss of control is also allocated to the internal return systems of Member States themselves. A 2024 communication expresses this most clearly, by calling on member states to be “more assertive on returns” since “one out of five return decisions taken is not effectively implemented”.³⁵ The response of Member States, according to the EC, has been characterized by fragmentation and a lack of proper implementation of EU rules on return. A much-cited phenomenon through which this lack of proper implementation gets substantiated is the previously mentioned deportation gap (Gibney 2008, see Stutz & Trauner 2022 and Scheel 2024 for critical accounts): the gap between the number of return orders issued and actual returns taking place.³⁶ The EC denounces Member States in firm language for not having their internal return policies on track, for example by allowing for “gaps” between asylum and return procedures³⁷, lengthy asylum procedures that lead to a lack of faith and trust in a fair and effective procedure on the part of applicants³⁸, difficulties in preventing absconding³⁹ and for not implementing existing policies to their fullest.⁴⁰ Fragmentation between member states is equally deemed problematic in terms of **legitimacy**. In the area of AVRR, it would undermine the trust of returnees and third

²⁹ COM(2021) 120 final, p.1

³⁰ COM(2021) 590 final; COM(2020) 609 final

³¹ COM(2011) 248 final

³² COM(2011) 76 final

³³ COM(2016) 385 final; COM(2017) 200 final; COM(2017) 471 final; COM(2017) 350 final; COM(2017) 669 final; COM(2017) 205 final; COM(2018) 634 final; COM(2021) 590 final

³⁴ COM(2015) 453 final; COM(2016) 385 final; COM(2017) 200 final; COM(2017) 471 final; COM(2017) 669 final; COM(2023) 45 final; COM(2021) 56 final

³⁵ COM(2024) 126 final

³⁶ COM(2024) 126 final; COM(2021) 56 final; COM(2020) 609 final; COM(2018) 798 final; COM(2016) 385 final

³⁷ COM(2021) 590 final

³⁸ COM(2021) 120 final

³⁹ COM(2021) 120 final; COM(2021) 590 final

⁴⁰ COM(2015) 453 final; COM(2017) 820 final; C 2017/432; COM(2017) 200 final; COM(2017) 558 final; COM(2018) 634 final; COM(2018) 303 final; COM(2022) 740 final

countries in the reintegration schemes provided in the EU and would, in turn, encourage onward migration.⁴¹ Not making use of EU readmission arrangements, in contrast, undermines credibility of the EU towards third countries – who are expected to apply the EURAs correctly – and could undermine human rights protection guarantees that these frameworks stipulate.⁴² In a later communication, the EC problematizes the fact that bilateral interest between member states and certain third countries at times seem to supersede collective, EU interests, while instead these relationships should be mobilized for the collective good of the EU.⁴³ Similarly, member states fail to share information on return amongst one another, for example on return decisions taken or residence permits withdrawn, which can ensure that renewed applications in another member state lead to a delay in return.⁴⁴ Member states, in short, do not seem to have “grip” on the issue of return, which results in a low return rate that continues to feature prominently in these documents.⁴⁵ The EC rarely takes blame themselves for this, as they mention to “[have] been supporting Member States in this process through both funding and operational support by the relevant EU Agencies”.⁴⁶

Concluding, the analysis of EC policy documents shows that its normative dimensions and ‘deep-seated presuppositions’ that inform the “problem” that return policy should solve has remained fairly stable. We see a clear and continuing securitization of illegalized migration, in which people on the move are explicitly and ostensibly portrayed as law-breaking, criminal threats to public security that merit an intervention on behalf of the EC. At the moment EU return policy started to consolidate in the early 2010s and accelerated by the so-called “refugee crisis” in 2015/2016, this security-orientation fused with a politics of care and compassion that sought to “assist” people on the move. This moment also showed that after a period in which EU return policy was set up, the EC understands the operational working of said policy as inadequate to control the phenomenon of illegalized migration. In the section below, I will detail the kind of policy instruments proposed to tackle this constructed problem.

Enforcement instruments: solutions to what problem?

Over the past two decades, the EC proposed and implemented a wide range of enforcement instruments that should “improve” return policy. To structure the discussion on its evolution below, I propose a twofold distinction in these enforcement instruments: between **direct** and **indirect** enforcement instruments and between those that seek to target the **internal** or **external dimension** of EU return policy. Direct and indirect measures can be distinguished based on their foreseen impact on closing the “deportation gap”: direct measures do this in a relatively straightforward manner, by for example detaining undocumented migrants for purposes of removal or by concluding readmission agreements that facilitate the issuing of substitute travel documents. Indirect measures, instead, only have a possible effect in the second instance, for example by restricting access to the labour market for undocumented migrants in Member States (assuming that this will disincentivize

⁴¹ COM(2021) 120; COM(2015) 453 final; COM(2014) 199 final;

⁴² COM(2011) 76 final, p.4

⁴³ COM(2017) 350 final; COM(2018) 303 final

⁴⁴ COM(2015) 453 final; COM(2017) 200 final

⁴⁵ COM(2015) 453 final; JOIN(2015) 40 final; COM(2015) 510 final; COM(2016) 385 final; COM(2017) 200 final; COM(2017) 350 final; COM(2018) 798 final; COM(2019) 481 final

⁴⁶ COM(2024) 126 final, p.9, also in COM(2021) 590 final; COM(2022) 740 final; COM(2017) 350 final; COM(2017) 558 final

undocumented stay) or by investing in diplomatic relations through liaison networks (assuming that this will lead to better cooperation on removal). The internal dimension comprises efforts to strengthen return procedures on the Member States territory, whereas the external dimension is concerned with political, practical, and technical cooperation with migrants' countries of citizenship, as well as measures that encourage return from "transit" (Slominski & Trauner 2021). This distinction is reflected in table 1 below, illustrated with examples.

Return policy's enforcement elements	Internal dimension	External dimension
Direct	<i>Pre-removal detention</i> <i>Frontex operational assistance</i> <i>AVRR assistance</i>	<i>Concluding EU-wide readmission agreements and arrangements</i> <i>Transit centres for AVRR/VHR</i>
Indirect	<i>(Financial) disincentives</i> <i>Share information between Member States</i> <i>Common definitions</i>	<i>Reintegration assistance</i> <i>Diplomatic liaison</i> <i>Technical innovations</i>

Table 1: Overview of enforcement elements core to EU return policy. Source: authors' own compilation.

As the table already hints at, the review of two decades worth of policy documents shows that a wide range of policy instruments have been proposed that seek to enforce return both internally and externally. Generally speaking, most of these policy instruments either seek to address the securitized nature of illegalized migration (fusing with more legalistic or humanitarian discourses) or reinstate the loss of control on the part of the EU – meaning that there is an overall conceptual match between the envisioned "policy problems" and "policy solutions" (Verloo 2005). In the paragraphs below, I will detail the most commonly proposed instruments and trends that shape the evolution of this policy field.

The internal dimension of EU Return Policy: common definitions and harmonizing implementation

On the internal dimension of EU return policy, we clearly see that the vast majority of proposed instruments across the span of two decades focus on (re)instating control over the phenomenon of illegalized migration, mainly through harmonizing the EU's response to it. There are only a few instruments that the EC proposes on the internal dimension that directly attempts to affect the composition, direction or volume of illegalized migration through return policy. One that is further specified below relates to calls on member states to make consequent use of pre-removal detention before effectuating removals.⁴⁷ Another instrument that appeared from 2005 onwards was the role of Frontex as an actor that might assist member states operationally in implementing their return

⁴⁷ COM(2015) 453 final; COM 2017/432; COM(2018) 634 final; COM(2021) 56 final; but also see C(2023) 1763 final

policy, and at some point post-2015 also initiate return operations independently.⁴⁸ The EC also allocates an important role to Frontex in further harmonizing the EU's approach to return, which will be further explained in the section below.

In contrast, there are a myriad of instruments proposed that influence illegalized migration solely in an indirect manner. A clear one linking illegalized migration to return is an early effort under the Tampere Program to propose sanctions to persons facilitating illegalized migration – either the movement of third country nationals as such or by employing them. Beyond criminally convicting these third persons, the EC also proposed stringent financial consequences, revealing that they understand illegalized migration as “business” or “industry” that third persons profit from.⁴⁹ Such financial disincentives, therefore, would make it unattractive to come or stay on EU territory. In the early 2000s, the EC also linked migration policy to other internal policy domains in the EU, such as labour policy. They put emphasis on the alleged linkages between illegalized migration and labour market needs, in the face of “changing economic and demographic needs of the European Union”.⁵⁰ While acknowledging the need for both high and low skilled migrant workers in the EU, the EC insists that “opening or re-opening legal channels for [labour] migration cannot be seen as a panacea against illegal immigration” as “illegal entry or residence should not lead to the desired stable form of residence”,⁵¹ - following a punitive approach to illegalized migrants.

Most proposed policy instruments in the first decade, however, attempted to **instate a sense of control** over illegalized migration and return on the part of the EC and do so in an indirect manner. As both the Tampere Program and the Hague Program explicitly sought to build a common EU return policy – both internally and externally – we see a myriad of proposals that centre on **Europeanizing** return policy. A very first way in which the EC tried to achieve this was by “learning” from the national measures that each member state independently had already developed to overcome various “obstacles” in the return procedure, whether related to the behaviour of individual migrants themselves, willingness to cooperate on the part of third-country governments, or more technical in nature.⁵² Referencing the need to exchange information, share knowledge and “best practices” returns frequently in later periods, including through actors such as Frontex and the European Migration Network, and by using shared technological tools like the Schengen Information System (SIS) to the fullest.⁵³ As a second step, the EC calls for common principles, definitions and standards on “illegal residence”, issuing return decisions and defining the “risk of absconding”, amongst others.⁵⁴ These accumulated in the 2008 EU Return Directive, after which discussions on clarifying the **implementation** of these standards took over.⁵⁵ Indeed, policy instruments that followed mostly referenced the already existing EU *aquis* on return and attempted to provide member states with tools to “better implement” these as to make returns “more effective”.⁵⁶ Some proposals that reoccur include the launch of an EU Return Fund to assist Member States in implementation efforts, organize joint return operations assisted by Frontex⁵⁷, and appoint a Special Representative on

⁴⁸ COM(2015) 240 final; see also COM(2015) 453 final; COM(2021) 590 final; COM(2021) 120 final

⁴⁹ COM(2001) 672 final

⁵⁰ COM(2001) 672 final

⁵¹ COM(2001) 672 final, p.6

⁵² COM(2001) 672 final; COM(2002) 564 final; COM(2003) 323 final; SEC(2004) 1349

⁵³ COM(2001) 672 final; COM(2003) 323 final; SEC(2004) 1349

⁵⁴ COM(2001) 672 final; COM(2002) 564 final; COM(2002) 175 final; COM(2002) 703 final; COM(2003) 323 final; COM(2006) 402 final; C 2005/0167 (COD)

⁵⁵ I.e., in COM(2010) 171; COM(2014) 199 final

⁵⁶ COM(2014) 199 final; COM(2014) 96 final

⁵⁷ C (2010/C 115/01); COM(2011) 743 final; COM(2014) 199 final

return to oversee the Europeanization of return policy.⁵⁸ A reoccurring instrument concerns technological innovations⁵⁹ such as the Integrated Return Management Application (IRMA)⁶⁰ and the Entry-Exit system⁶¹ that should ensure commonality across the EU, amongst others by mutually recognizing return orders issued in different member states.

Measures to Europeanize the internal dimension of EU return policy intensified from 2015 onwards, which is most clearly visible in proposals to increase the role of Frontex. Most proposals call for a widening of their mandate, so as to have them independently initiate and operate Joint Return Operations (JROs), assist in identification of illegalized migrants, and to further streamline their work with operational assistance in the member states.⁶² The 2017 action plan “On a more effective return policy in the European Union” and its Return Handbook furthermore details how current EU rules are differently implemented by various member states, with various measures not being used to the degree that the EC believes they should. While some of these are mostly procedural, such as the need to systematically issue return decisions⁶³, most reinforce the securitized understanding of illegalized migration and return. The EC for example proposes that member states need to use the “full flexibility” of the Return Directive, by accelerating asylum procedures for applicants from so-called “safe countries of origin”⁶⁴, providing less safeguards by avoiding repeated *non-refoulement* assessments,⁶⁵ making use of detention for the full 18 months,⁶⁶ and using emergency clauses and simplified procedures when applicable.⁶⁷ A clear and extreme case comprises issuing return decisions for unaccompanied minors, which is not applied uniformly across Member States even though the Return Directive in principle allows for this. The EC problematizes this practice, by arguing that the

“return of an unaccompanied minor to the third country of origin and reunification with the family may be in the best interests of the child. The prohibition to issue return decisions to unaccompanied minors, which exists in the national legislation of several Member States, does not give full effect to the Member States' obligation to take due account of the child's best interests, and to pay attention to the circumstances of each individual case. Such prohibitions can create unintended consequences for illegal immigration, inciting unaccompanied minors to embark on perilous journeys in order to reach the Union”.⁶⁸

Under the guise of humanitarian language, the EC encourages member states to issue return orders – and thereby rendering them deportable – as return would be in their “best interests” and can allegedly prevent embarkation in the first place. A little further in the same document, the EC encourages member states to use detention for unaccompanied minors: “[...] an absolute prohibition of detention in such cases, may not give full effect to the obligation to take all necessary measures to ensure return, leading to annulment of return operations due to absconding”.⁶⁹ This shows the fusion of humanitarian language and security measures taken to control, in this instance, the return of unaccompanied minors from the member states. The push for a Europeanized return policy similarly

⁵⁸ COM(2002) 564 final; Council 2005/C 53/01, p.6; COM(2006) 402 final; SEC(2004)1349; COM(2002) 175 final

⁵⁹ C (2010/C 115/01); COM(2011) 743 final

⁶⁰ See <https://www.frontex.europa.eu/return-and-reintegration/return-operations/return-digitalisation/>

⁶¹ COM(2021) 120 final; C(2023) 1763 final

⁶² COM(2015) 240 final; see also COM(2015) 453 final; COM(2021) 590 final; COM(2021) 120 final

⁶³ C 2017/432

⁶⁴ C 2017/432; COM(2017) 200 final; COM(2018) 634 final; COM(2019) 481 final

⁶⁵ COM(2017) 200 final

⁶⁶ COM(2018) 634 final

⁶⁷ COM(2015) 453 final; COM(2017) 200 final; COM(2017) 558 final;

⁶⁸ C 2017/432, p.3

⁶⁹ C 2017/432, p.3

transposes in the EC's approach to AVRR, especially under the New Pact on Migration and Asylum (2020). Their 2021 communication on "the EU strategy on voluntary return and reintegration" problematizes the fragmentation of approaches to AVR in the EU, especially when it comes to different levels of cooperation with third countries, which would "undermine the trust of returnees and of third countries in the system and their willingness to engage".⁷⁰ The lack of a consistent approach, according to the EC, in turn complicates the implementation of and overall cooperation on EU return arrangements and agreements.⁷¹ From that communication on, the EC has initiated several enforcement instruments to build this common approach for AVR. The basis for this common framework comes from the new involvement of Frontex in AVR, by becoming "the operational arm of the common EU system of returns", now for the first time also including AVR.⁷² They should provide operational assistance to Member States through the European Union Reintegration Programme (formally Joint Reintegration Service, JRS) in both AVR and reintegration, by developing outreach campaigns to migrants, developing joint reintegration services and coordinating a new EU framework on return counselling that includes a common curriculum for counsellors.⁷³ A similar, coordinative role, is allocated to the newly established Return Coordinator and the High Level Network for Return. These are specifically designed to provide technical support to the member states, bring different strands of return policy together, and "promote a more coherent approach to reintegration assistance in relation to specific partner countries".⁷⁴

Finally, in more recent years, we also see an emphasis on the role of individual member states in return as opposed to a Europeanized approach. Assisted by Frontex, the so-called "return sponsorship"⁷⁵ would allow member states to "sponsor" a returnee on behalf of another member states who face "migratory pressure". The new member state would provide for return counselling, financial or practical support, or even lead policy dialogue with the third country, or "pay" the original member state to do this on their territory – at their discretion. Academic accounts have already predicted that this system is one of high political stakes for the EU, with potentially only low gains (Diez et al. 2021).

The external dimension of EU Return Policy: (un)equal partnerships and mainstreaming return

The external dimension of return policy gained traction predominantly from the Hague Program (2005-2009) onwards but has always been acknowledged as of core importance to the EU. In all documents that touch upon this external dimension, the need to "step up" cooperation with third countries features prominently.⁷⁶ The primary, more direct policy instrument through which the EC seeks to effectuate deportation orders and ensure "collaboration" with third countries are so-called EU-wide readmission agreements (EURAs) - 18 of such agreements are concluded to date, as figure 1 below demonstrates.⁷⁷ With the Amsterdam Treaty in 1999, the European Commission first got competences to negotiate such agreements on behalf of the Union as a whole, reflecting the Europeanization of return policy's external dimension. Member states are in principle restricted from

⁷⁰ COM(2021) 120 final, but see also C (2010/C 115/01); COM(2014) 199 final under the Stockholm Program

⁷¹ COM(2021) 120 final, p.4

⁷² COM(2021) 120 final, p.9

⁷³ COM(2021) 120 final

⁷⁴ COM(2021) 120 final, p.9

⁷⁵ COM(2020) 609 final

⁷⁶ C (2010/C 115/01); COM(2011) 76 final

⁷⁷ For a full list, see https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/irregular-migration-and-return/humane-and-effective-return-and-readmission-policy_en

conducting separate negotiations with third countries in case the EC is negotiating with said third country, or such a process is in consideration by the Council (Molinari 2021).

Figure 1: Evolution of number of EU-wide agreements over time. Source: Cassarino (2022).

At the same time, bilateral agreements (as well as more informal arrangements) between member states and third countries already existed and are continued to be negotiated until today, as shown in Figure 2. In these first communications, the EC assessed bilateral agreements are equally beneficial as EU-wide ones.⁷⁸ In the EC's evaluation of their common readmission policy, however, their continued use is problematized in case EURAs entered into force, detailing that "the Commission will closely monitor the correct implementation of EURAs by MS and, if necessary, consider legal steps in case of incorrect or lack of implementation".⁷⁹ In later communications, similarly, the tension between bilateral and EU-wide interests appear again, with the EC arguing that bilateral interests seem to supersede collective, EU interests and usage of EURAs while instead these relationships should be mobilized for the collective good of the EU.⁸⁰

⁷⁸ COM(2002) 564 final; COM(2002) 703 final

⁷⁹ COM(2011) 76 final, p.4

⁸⁰ COM(2017) 350 final; COM(2018) 303 final

Figure 2: Evolution of number of bilateral agreements between EU Member States and third countries over time. Source: Cassarino (2022).

Early on in 2002, the Commission’s Green Paper emphasized the importance of a common policy on readmission and made first steps to formulate criteria that would guide the choice of countries with whom to negotiate such agreements and introduced “readmission standard clauses” to be implemented in all EU agreements with third countries. In the same paper, the EC problematizes the “willingness” of third states to cooperate on concluding such agreements in particular, and on taking their nationals back in general, by arguing that

“readmission agreements are solely in the interest of the Community; their successful conclusion depends very much on the “leverage” at the Commission’s disposal. In that context it is important to note that, in the field of JHA, there is little that can be offered in return. In particular visa facilitation or the lifting of visa requirement can be a realistic option in exceptional cases only (e.g. Hong Kong, Macao); in most cases it is not”.⁸¹

In almost all documents that followed, negotiations on concluding such readmission agreements are described as “difficult” and “lengthy”, therefore meriting a different approach, which was envisioned to indirectly help the take up of readmissions.⁸² This new approach kicked off most clearly with the Global Approach to Migration and Mobility in 2011 and the Partnership Framework in 2016, which got characterized by a “flexible and tailor-made approach, depending on the overall political dialogue between the EU and the non-EU country and on both the EU’s interests and the interests and needs of its partner”.⁸³ Indeed, this moment marked a shift in the policy instrument in two ways. First, the nature of readmission agreements changed: from narrow, formal agreements on

⁸¹ COM(2002) 175 final, p.23

⁸² COM(2011) 743 final; SEC(2011) 1353 final; JOIN(2015) 40 final; COM(2016) 385 final; COM(2017) 205 final; COM(2018) 798 final; COM(2021) 56 final

⁸³ SEC(2011) 1353 final, p.11

readmission only to more informal and widened arrangements (Carrera 2018) under the header of “Mobility Partnerships” or a “Common Agenda on Migration and Mobility” (CAMM).⁸⁴ Especially the CAMMs were designed for situations when “both sides want to establish an advanced level of cooperation, but where one side or the other is not ready to enter into the full set of obligations and commitments”.⁸⁵ These thus aim to establish the same kind of cooperation – on return and readmission – but do so in more informal and “less visible” manners, so as to avoid parliamentary scrutiny or domestic public outcry, as various academics argue (Carrera et al. 2018; Cassarino 2018; Slominski and Trauner 2021). Figure 3 precisely shows that this informalization of EU readmission cooperation (Cassarino 2018) indeed grew over time, especially with countries in Africa and Asia.

Figure 3: Evolution of non-bindingness of EU Readmission agreements over time. Source: Cassarino (2022).

Second, these instruments centred incentives by means of **issue linkage** to convince third countries to cooperate with the EU. Guised under the language of “partnerships”, the EC proposes a broad package of measures that are believed to be mutually beneficial for the EU and third countries, such as opportunities for labour migration. The linking of visa facilitation to cooperation on return, therefore, takes centre stage in in these “partnerships”: they would “offer visa facilitation based on a simultaneous negotiated readmission agreement. A more for more approach, implying an element of conditionality, should continue to be applied as a way to increase transparency and speed up progress towards concluding these agreements”.⁸⁶ Figure 4 below shows that since 2008, readmission agreements and arrangements have indeed been made that include visa facilitation – albeit selectively. This has mostly been successful with countries in the EU Neighbourhood (Eastern

⁸⁴ C (2010/C 115/01; COM(2010) 171); COM(2011) 248 final

⁸⁵ SEC(2011) 1353 final, p.11

⁸⁶ SEC(2011) 1353 final, p.11

Europe), whereas countries in Africa, the Americas and Asia tend to benefit less from this measure (see also Reslow 2013; Trauner and Kruse 2008).

Figure 4: Evolution of visa facilitation tied to EU Readmission agreements over time. Source: Cassarino (2022).

EC documents however simultaneously mention other possible linkages between policy fields in the external dimension, which include cooperation in the area of trade and business,⁸⁷ student mobility⁸⁸, migration management⁸⁹ and providing for various kinds of technical and financial assistance to “enable third countries to respond to readmission requests”.⁹⁰ While in some instances such “capacity building” relates to providing for development fundings to “enable” for the reintegration of returnees, proposals often include measures to finance new civil registries to be built in third countries such as Senegal, or biometric databases that can easily be consulted when a readmission request is made.⁹¹ Interestingly, such “capacity building” thus merits direct interference of the EU on internal matters in third countries: when it comes to managing populations through registrations and (biometric) oversight, but also when it comes to how said countries’ should discuss return with their citizens. An EC communication from 2017 on the external dimension details that

efforts need to be stepped up to help [sic] partners communicate to their citizens that cooperating on readmission is part of a comprehensive and balanced relationship with the EU and its Member States

⁸⁷ COM(2011) 743 final; COM(2011) 248 final

⁸⁸ COM(2017) 205 final

⁸⁹ COM(2016) 385 final

⁹⁰ COM(2011) 76 final, p.3; see also COM(2011) 743 final; COM(2011) 248 final; COM(2011) 76 final; COM(2014) 96 final COM(2015) 453 final; COM(2015) 240 final; COM(2016) 385 final; COM(2017) 200 final Annex 1; COM(2019) 481 final

⁹¹ COM(2015) 453 final; COM(2017) 350 final; COM(2017) 205 final

and is key to discourage further irregular departures, which put at risk the life of many of their compatriots.⁹²

As this example also highlights, the coupling of return with development financing and “capacity building” also proliferates from the early 2010s onwards.⁹³ Development assistance is on the one hand offered as incentive to cooperate on readmissions⁹⁴ but the EC also attempts to instrumentalize the “developmental benefits” of (return) migration for the benefit of third countries involved. Return is understood as a core mechanism that effectuates the so-called “triple win” (see also Sinatti 2016): making the developmental potential of migration beneficial to the EU, third countries and migrant themselves. This starts from the premise that “return, either temporary or permanent, can bring back human, financial, economic and social capital to developing countries. Return programmes should therefore explicitly take this dimension into account”.⁹⁵ Linkages are predominantly made to return policies and programmes for diaspora members and other persons with legal status to wish to return to their (ancestral) country of nationality, either temporarily or permanently, to combat issues like “brain drain” and the “adverse use of remittances”.⁹⁶ The EC proposed measures to transfer pension rights, recognize qualifications that migrants have received in the EU, and facilitate temporary return of diaspora for purposes of development and capacity building.⁹⁷ In later communications on AVRR, the developmental potential of people who have received a return order is similarly foregrounded (see Marino and Liettaert 2022 for a critical account).⁹⁸

While the EURA’s are by and large the policy instrument most discussed in the documents, and where most “instrument settings” are changed in order to ensure that third countries are keen to conclude these, there are few further measures that attempt to effectuate return. One relates to the implementation of readmission arrangements or agreements: as the implementation on the part of third countries is problematized⁹⁹, the EC promotes measures like implementation protocols (see figure 5) to be concluded with new arrangements, as well as regular meetings of so-called Joint Readmission Committees (JRCs) or Joint Working Groups. These latter are meant as “control devices” to track whether implementation of the agreement is delivered “as expected”.¹⁰⁰ If this is not the case, in accordance with Article 25a(2) of the Visa Code, punitive measures can be initiated against individual third countries.¹⁰¹ Another more direct measure are efforts to facilitate AVRR from so-called “transit countries”. This idea first arose in a migration-development communication in 2013, when so-called “Migration and Mobility Resource Centres” financed by the EU would provide non-EU nationals interested in moving to the EU with pre-departure information, as well as information on return and reintegration assistance.¹⁰² From 2015 onwards, such “humanitarian” measures broadened and became embedded in the EC’s broader approach to AVRR, as facilitating pre-arrival returns from “transit” is understood as “less politicized” and helping to prevent “loss of life” *en*

⁹² COM(2017) 350 final, p.5

⁹³ But see COM(2002) 703 final; COM(2003) 323 final

⁹⁴ I.e., in COM(2021) 56 final; COM(2017) 200 final Annex 1

⁹⁵ COM(2005) 390 final, p. 12

⁹⁶ COM(2005) 390 final; SEC(2009) 766 final; SEC(2011) 1353 final; COM(2013) 292 final

⁹⁷ COM(2005) 390 final

⁹⁸ COM(2021) 120 final

⁹⁹ I.e., in COM(2020) 609 final; COM(2023) 45 final

¹⁰⁰ COM(2016) 385 final; COM(2017) 200 final Annex 1; COM(2017) 350 final; COM(2021) 56 final

¹⁰¹ See a.o. COM(2023) 568 final

¹⁰² COM(2013) 292 final

route.¹⁰³ This is often achieved through the Joint EU-IOM Cooperation framework, established in 2015.¹⁰⁴

Figure 5: Evolution of EU Readmission agreements with implementation protocols over time. Source: Cassarino (2022).

In the external dimension, there are a myriad of other instruments that indirectly seek to enhance the “return rate”. One concerns bettering diplomatic channels, especially in view of better identifying third country nationals. Together with Frontex’ involvement and newly initiated joint identification missions to obtain travel documents for non-citizens¹⁰⁵, European liaison officers play an important role. Whereas there have been Member State liaison officers already posted in third countries for a longer time, the 2018 recast proposal for a European network of immigration liaison officers explicitly specified the need to “deploy them to the benefit of the EU as a whole”.¹⁰⁶ They would need to assist in identification of third country nationals and provide post-arrival assistance to returnees. Finally, and similar to the internal dimension, the EC presents technological innovations as measures to “smoothen” the return procedure. The “Return Case Management System”¹⁰⁷ by IOM would for example help to facilitate the actual implementation of RA agreements, with necessary (biometric) data stored and shared between the EU and third countries.

¹⁰³ COM(2015) 453 final; JOIN(2015) 40 final; COM(2016) 385 final; COM(2017) 820 final; COM(2017) 471 final; COM(2017) 350 final; JOIN(2017) 4 final; COM(2017) 669 final; COM(2019) 481 final

¹⁰⁴ COM(2021) 590 final; COM(2021) 120 final; COM(2023) 45 final; COM(2024) 126 final

¹⁰⁵ COM(2017) 200 final; COM(2024) 126 final

¹⁰⁶ COM(2018) 303 final

¹⁰⁷ COM(2021) 56 final, see also

https://eea.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbdl666/files/documents/ENG_MODEL%20RCMS%20brochure%20%28E-PDF%20pages%29%202020.pdf

Discussion and conclusion

This report has provided an overview of the developments in EU Return Policy since its inception in the early 2000s until present-day operation under the New Pact on Migration and Asylum. After introducing deportation as a complicated and self-constrained power, the report conceptualized EU return policy as linked to the international management of mobile populations in two ways. On the one hand, return policy should be understood as a highly selective *enforcement mechanism* that is aimed to ensure that bodies are relocated to the territories they legally belong, typically defined in terms of nationality ('who *is* where'). On the other hand, return policy also is a *reclassification mechanism* by defining which immigrants do not or no longer deserve to be a member of the society, such as when residence permit holders lose their right to stay because of having committed certain crimes' ('who *belongs* where'). In both senses – as an *enforcement mechanism* and *reclassification mechanism* – return policy is also a normative vehicle that substantiates membership ideals. Indeed, return policy implicitly sustains the common norms, ideals and identity of nation states by producing migrant deportability, declaring who cannot (or no longer) be part of the community of value (Anderson 2013).

The empirical section of this report predominantly focused on outlining what the evolution of EU Return Policy *as an enforcement mechanism* looked like across the past two decades. Yet, its first part also outlined the conceived image of the illegalized migrant suitable for expulsion from the EU's normative community of value. This part showed that the EC policy documents reflect an image of illegalized migrants in need of return ostensibly in a securitized manner, as individuals breaching the law, engaging in criminal activities and taking advantage of the (mal)functioning of EU's internal migration policy. This is amplified across time, when the documents increasingly reflect a sense of "loss of control" over migratory movements within and to the EU, epitomized in the figure of the "deportation gap" (Gibney 2008). This securitization of migration remains remarkably stable across time and fuses with a more humanitarian image of returnees in need of "assistance" on the part of the EU around 2010. The same goes for third countries, who, according to the documents, are to be assisted in their migration management efforts through "capacity building" and "development assistance" in order to "reintegrate" returnees back into the territorial spaces in which they allegedly belong. As previous literature suggested, such humanitarian imperatives are mobilized to overcome the liberal constraint that liberal democracies face in executing their sovereign powers (i.e., Gibney 1999, Newman 2017, Cleton 2022). These normative policy goals and orientations thus imply that the European Union as a community of value is no place for "criminal-others" who breach EU legislation yet are at the same time in need of assistance on the part of that same community for purposes of their "reintegration".

When it comes to the evolution of enforcement mechanisms in the area of return, however, we see a different picture emerging. As the second part of the empirical section showed, a myriad of policy instruments were proposed, developed and slightly altered to ensure the departure of illegalized migrants from the EU or encourage it from spaces of "transit". Internally, most efforts have been made to harmonize approaches between member states: first in setting a common understanding of definitions, standards and safeguards used, and from the 2010s onwards on the level of implementation practices. Instruments related to funds, technological innovations, assistance by EU-actors like Frontex, fora to exchange for "best practices" and setting common curricula for AVRR counselling are amongst the instruments proposed that should lead to harmonization in the implementation phase. On the external dimension, we see a number of changes to the instrument settings of readmission agreements over the years, together with further efforts to enhance the

implementation of these agreements – via capacity building, technological investments and extensive liaison networks, amongst others. Here as well, harmonization is seemingly understood as a way to get “more grip” on illegalized migration.

In short, we thus see a sharp difference between, on the one hand, a rather stable understanding of illegalized migration in securitized language, as a phenomenon that the EU “lost control” of and, with on the other hand a myriad of return policy instruments proposed to counter this alleged “loss of control” and regain a sense of security. Interestingly, despite all of these measures proposed by the EC, their own core criticism on the functioning of both return policy’s internal and external dimension remains the same: the existence of the “deportation gap”. The New Pact on Migration and Asylum in 2020, the EC’s paragraph on return policy starts with arguing that “EU migration rules can be credible only if those who do not have the right to stay in the EU are effectively returned. Currently, only about a third of people ordered to return from Member States actually leave”.¹⁰⁸ Despite all of the measures proposed, altered and (re)invented across the past two decades, the EC thus concludes that return policy is still, in their own words, “failing” and is not leading to a (re)gained sense of control. Instead of proposing further measures that seek to do exactly the same – reinstate control through Europeanization and securitization as visible in the 2021 common AVR policy and 2023 strategy on return – we would like to conclude this report by urging the EC not to rethink return’s policy instruments, but rather, to speak with Hall (1993), their underlying paradigm to illegalized migration and the alleged “solutions” that return policy would bring. One alternative way of imagining the “problem” of illegalized migration would be to lessen the pervasive securitized orientation and punitive approach taken, and instead focus on the labour market potential of illegalized migrants in an aging EU,¹⁰⁹ for example by taking the idea of “circular labour mobility” policies seriously and allow illegalized residents present on EU territory to work. Alternatively, following de Haas (2024), the EC could let go of the imaginary of illegalized migration as a problem to be controlled and instead present a more evidence-based, long-term vision of migration as an intrinsic part of global processes of social change and development, rather than an *a priori* problem to be solved. In the absence of such a paradigmatic rethinking, the gap between stated enforcement ambitions and enforcement outcomes is unlikely to become much smaller, especially for EU Member States that have already made significant investments in their return policies. Policymakers should then accept that the costs and benefits of investments in their return policies – be it in the form of *enforcement* or *reclassification* – must be balanced against the costs and benefits of various forms of non-enforcement, including regularization and continued stay. While different actors weigh these costs and benefits differently (see also Legomsky 2009), it is important that European citizens are well-informed that such a realistic balancing act is both inevitable and desirable.

¹⁰⁸ COM(2020) 609 final, p.7

¹⁰⁹ As already acknowledged in COM(2001) 672 final

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Annex

Annex 1 – list of European Commission policy documents analysed

Code	Year	Document title
COM(2001) 672 final	2001	Communication from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament on a Common Policy on Illegal Migration
COM(2002) 564 final	2002	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament on A Community Return Policy on Illegal Residents
COM(2002) 175 final	2002	Green Paper on a Community Return Policy on Illegal Residents
COM(2002) 703 final	2002	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament on Integrating Migration Issues in the European Union's External Relations with Third Countries
COM(2003) 323 final	2003	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament on the Development of a Common Policy on Illegal Migration. Immigration, Smuggling and Trafficking of Human Beings, External Borders and the Return of Illegal Residents.
COM(2003) 104 final	2003	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament. Wider Europe — Neighbourhood: A New Framework for Relations with our Eastern and Southern Neighbours
C 2004/573/EC	2004	Council Decision of 29 April 2004 on the organisation of joint flights for removals from the territory of two or more Member States, of third-country nationals who are subjects of individual removal orders
COM(2004) 373 final	2004	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament. European Neighbourhood Policy: Strategy Paper
SEC(2004) 1349	2004	Commission Staff Working Document. Annual report on the development of a common policy on illegal immigration, smuggling and trafficking of human beings, external borders, and the return of illegal residents
C 9778/2/05 REV 2	2005	Council and Commission Action Plan implementing the Hague Programme on strengthening freedom, security and justice in the European Union
COM(2005) 390 final	2005	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Migration and Development: Some concrete orientations

COM(2005) 491 final	2005	Communication from the Commission. A strategy on the External Dimension of the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice
CME 2005	2005	Twenty Guidelines of the Committee of Minister of Europe on Forced Return
C 2005/C 53/01	2005	The Hague Programme: Strengthening Freedom, Security and Justice in the European Union
COM(2006) 402 final	2006	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament on Policy priorities in the fight against illegal immigration of third-country nationals
C 2005/0167 (COD)	2006	Proposal for a European Parliament and Council Directive on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals
SEC(2009) 766 final	2009	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Justice, Freedom and Security in Europe since 2005: An evaluation of the Hague Programme and Action Plan. An extended report on the evaluation of the Hague Programme
C (2010/C 115/01)	2010	Notices from European Union Institutions, Bodies, Offices and Agencies. European Council. The Stockholm Programme – an Open and Secure Union
COM(2010) 171	2010	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Delivering an area of freedom, security and justice for Europe's citizens Action Plan Implementing the Stockholm Programme
COM(2011) 743 final	2011	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. The Global Approach to Migration and Mobility
SEC(2011) 1353 final	2011	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. The Global Approach to Migration and Mobility
COM(2011) 248 final	2011	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Communication on migration
COM(2011) 76 final	2011	Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council. Evaluation of EU Readmission Agreements

COM(2013) 292 final	2013	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Maximising the Development Impact of Migration. The EU contribution for the UN High-level Dialogue and next steps towards broadening the development-migration nexus
COM(2014) 199 final	2014	Communication from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament on EU Return Policy
COM(2014) 96 final	2014	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Report on the implementation of the Global Approach to Migration and Mobility 2012-2013
COM(2015) 453 final	2015	Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council. EU Action Plan on Return
JOIN(2015) 40 final	2015	Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council. Addressing the Refugee Crisis in Europe: The Role of EU External Action
COM(2015) 240 final	2015	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. A European Agenda on Migration
COM(2015) 510 final	2015	Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council and the Council. Managing the refugee crisis: State of Play of the Implementation of the Priority Actions under the European Agenda on Migration
COM(2016) 960 final	2016	Report from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council and the Council. Second Progress Report: First Deliverables on the Partnership Framework with third countries under the European Agenda on Migration
COM(2016) 700 final	2016	Report from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council and the Council. First Progress Report on the Partnership Framework with third countries under the European Agenda on Migration
COM(2016) 385 final	2016	Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council and the European Investment Bank on establishing a new Partnership Framework with third countries under the European Agenda on Migration
COM(2016) 85 final	2016	Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on the State of Play of Implementation of the Priority Actions under the European Agenda on Migration
COM(2017) 200 final Annex 1	2017	Annex to the Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on a more Effective Return Policy in the European Union – a Renewed Action Plan

COM(2017) 820 final	2017	Commission contribution to the EU Leaders' thematic debate on a way forward on the external and the internal dimension of migration policy
COM 2017/432	2017	Commission Recommendation (EU) 2017/432 of 7 March 2017 on making returns more effective when implementing the Directive 2008/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council
COM(2017) 200 final	2017	Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on a More Effective Return Policy in the European Union – a Renewed Action Plan
COM(2017) 558 final	2017	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on the Delivery of the European Agenda on Migration
COM(2017) 471 final	2017	Report from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council and the Council. Fifth Progress Report on the Partnership Framework with third
COM(2017) 350 final	2017	Report from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council and the Council. Fourth Progress Report on the Partnership Framework with third
JOIN(2017) 4 final	2017	Joint Communication to the European Parliament, the European Council and the Council. Migration on the Central Mediterranean route. Managing flows, saving lives
COM(2017) 669 final	2017	Report from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council and the Council. Progress report on the European Agenda on Migration
C(2017) 1600	2017	Commission Recommendation (EU) 2017/2338 of 16 November 2017 establishing a common 'Return Handbook' to be used by Member States' competent authorities when carrying out return-related tasks
COM(2017) 205 final	2017	Report from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council and the Council. Third Progress Report on the Partnership Framework with third countries
COM(2018) 798 final	2018	Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council and the Council. Managing Migration in all its Aspects: Progress under the European Agenda on Migration
COM(2018) 634 final	2018	Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals (recast)
COM(2018) 303 final	2018	Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the creation of a European network of immigration liaison officers (recast)

COM(2019) 481 final	2019	Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council and the Council. Progress report on the Implementation of the European Agenda on Migration
COM(2020) 609 final	2020	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on a New Pact on Migration and Asylum
COM(2021) 590 final	2021	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on the Report on Migration and Asylum
COM(2021) 56 final	2021	Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council. Enhancing cooperation on return and readmission as part of a fair, effective and comprehensive EU migration policy
COM(2021) 120 final	2021	Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council. The EU strategy on voluntary return and reintegration
COM(2022) 740 final	2022	Communication from the Commission to the council and the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on the Report on Migration and Asylum
C(2023) 1763 final	2023	Commission Recommendation (EU) of 16.3.2023 on mutual recognition of return decisions and expediting returns when implementing Directive 2008/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council
COM(2023) 45 final	2023	Policy document. Towards an operational strategy for more effective returns
COM(2023) 568 final	2023	Proposal for a Council Implementing Decision on the suspension of certain provisions of Regulation (EC) 810/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council with respect to Ethiopia
COM(2024) 126 final	2024	Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council and the Council. Striking a balance on migration: an approach that is both fair and firm

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